

Formation Constants of Complexes of Thiophene-2-aldoxime and its 5-Methyl Derivative with Metal Ions.

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Formation constants of complexes formed by Thiophene-2-aldoxime(II), 5-Methyl-thiophene-2-aldoxime(II) with metal ions like Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), Ag(I) and Tl(I) are measured at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$ and at 0.1M NaClO₄ ionic strength. Metal-sulphur interaction is suggested for Zn(II) complex with I and II. Irving-William's order is not followed by the divalent metal ions of the first transitional series. The order is Cu > Co > Mn > Zn > Ni.

The order $\log K_2 > \log K_1$, for Zn(II) and Ni(II) complexes of both the ligands have been found.

ALDOXIMES are often found to form fairly strong complexes with metal ions. Studies of thiophene-2-aldoxime (I) and 5-Methyl-thiophene-2-aldoxime (II) has been described here. (I) was used as an analytical reagent for Pd(II) by Tandon et al¹. Coakley and co-workers² have prepared a number of complexes with (I) with chlorides of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Pd(II) and Cd(II) in ethanolic solution. Survey of literature shows that study of formation constant with this ligand has not been done. We have therefore measured the formation constants of complexes of (I) and (II) with metal ions like Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), Ag(I) and Tl(I). These metal ions have soft, mixed soft and hard characters.

The methyl group in 5-position in (II) being an electron repelling group will partially reduce the electron withdrawing effect of the aromatic ring from the side chain. Co-ordination can take place at N atom and if possible at the sulphur atom of the ring.

Experimental

0.04 M solutions of metal perchlorates were prepared as before^{3,4}. Thiophene-2-aldoxime and 5-methyl-thiophene-2-aldoxime were prepared respectively from thiophene-2-aldehyde and 5-methyl-

thiophene-2-aldehyde (received from K and K laboratories, Inc., USA.) by the method of Tandon et al¹. 0.04 M solutions of the oximes (ligands) were prepared by dissolving calculated amount of the ligand in water-dioxan mixture. Solutions of NaClO₄ (1M), HClO₄ (0.1M) and NaOH(0.1M) were prepared in the usual way^{1,2}.

Titration of (i) 20ml 0.0025M HClO₄ (Blank Titration), (ii) 0.0025M HClO₄+0.005M ligand ('Ligand Titration') and (iii) 0.0025M HClO₄+0.005M Ligand+0.001M Metal perchlorate ('Metal Titration') with 0.1M carbonate free NaOH solution by Bjerrum Calvin pH titration technique⁵ as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁶ were done as before^{3,4} in 50% v/v water-dioxan medium ($\mu=0.1M$ NaClO₄; $t=30^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$).

Results and Discussion

For the determinations of proton-ligand stability constants $\log \bar{n}_A / (1-\bar{n}_A)$ were then plotted against B-values whereby straight lines are obtained.

From these straight lines, values of $\log P K_1^H$ were obtained from the relation $\log P K_1^H = B + \log \frac{\bar{n}_A}{1-\bar{n}_A}$, and these values are given in Table I.

Determination of Metal-Ligand Stability Constants.

For the determination of metal ligand stability constants, \bar{n} and P^L were first calculated in the

usual way⁶. Formation curves are then obtained by plotting \bar{n} against P^L for all metal-ligand pairs and these curves are shown in figures 1 and 2.

These values of stability constants are given in Table I. Maximum \bar{n} values reached by the complexes are also shown in the Table I.

Value of $\log \frac{P^H}{K_1}$ of thiophene-2-aldoxime is

Fig. 1. Formation curves for metal complexes of thiophene-2-aldoxime.

From the nature of the formation curves it is seen⁷ that values of $\log K_1$ are not much different from those of $\log K_2$ for most systems where both 1:1 and 1:2 complexes are formed. Method of interpolation at half \bar{n} values may give erroneous result in such cases [$\log(K_1/K_2) \geq 2.5$]; so method of least squares was used for the determinations of these constants. For systems where only 1:1 complexes were formed values of $\log K_1$ were obtained from the relation,

$$\log K_1 = P^L + \log \frac{\bar{n}}{1-\bar{n}}$$

11.58. The 5-methyl-derivative has slightly higher value, 11.68. This implies that the electron shift from the side chain to the aromatic π ring in case of (I) has been partially offset by the electron repelling methyl group in the 5-methyl derivative. The order of stabilities with both the ligands (I) and (II) is $Hg > Cu > Co > Mn > Zn > Cd > Ni > Ag(I) > Tl(I)$. The stabilities are expected to increase from the complexes of the 2-aldoxime to those of the 5-methyl derivative. This is observed in the 1:1 complexes of Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Ag(I). But the reverse is true for Co(II), Mn(II), Ni(II) and Hg(II)

Table 1. Stability constants of metal complexes of thiophene-2-aldoxime and its 5-methyl derivative in 50% v/v H₂O dioxan medium ($\mu=0.1M$ NaClO₄; $t=30^{\circ}\pm 0.1$).

Acids	H ⁺			Zn ⁺²			Cu ⁺²			Co ⁺²			Mn ⁺²	
	log $P K_1^H$	log K ₁	log K ₂	Max. \bar{n}	log K ₁	log K ₂	Max \bar{n}	log K ₁	log K ₂	Max \bar{n}	log K ₁	log K ₂	Max \bar{n}	Max \bar{n}
T-2-OXM	11.58	6.51	7.71	1.67	9.26	8.35	1.21	9.20	8.26	1.60	8.07	5.69	1.06	
5-Me-T-2 20 × M	11.68	7.09	7.15	1.09	9.31	8.78	1.06	7.69	5.19	1.00	7.01	4.48	0.90	
Acids	Ni ⁺²			Hg ⁺²			Cd ⁺²		Ag ⁺¹		Tl ⁺¹			
	log K ₁	log K ₂	Max \bar{n}	log K ₁	log K ₂	Max \bar{n}	log K ₁	Max \bar{n}	log K ₁	Max \bar{n}	log K ₁	Max \bar{n}		
T-2-OXM	5.81	5.99	1.24	9.85	8.05	1.40	6.27	0.57	4.20	0.62	3.15	0.11		
5-Me-T-2 0 × M	5.28	6.44	1.24	9.59	7.74	1.29	6.33	0.70	4.23	0.75	—	—		

complexes. This decrease of stabilities from ligand I to II can be explained for the particular cases by the steric hindrance of the methyl group in the 5-position adjacent to the sulphur. This explanation, however, is based on the presumption that sulphur in the ring is involved in co-ordination.

Fig. 2. Formation curves for metal complexes of 5-methyl-thiophene-2-aldoxime.

Tl(I) does not appreciably react with the 5-methyl derivative and forms a weak complex with I, the maximum \bar{n} being 0.11. The order of stabilities Zn > Ni has been found with the complexes of Zn(II) and Ni(II) with both the ligands. Coakley et al.² have prepared complex of I with ZnCl₂. From the I.R. spectral studies of this complex they inferred M-S bonding. If in the present study Zn(II), with d¹⁰ system, is assumed to form M-S π bond, the order can be explained. Such order with sulphur containing ligands is found by many workers³.

Mercury(II) forms the strongest complexes with both the ligands I and II. It cannot be said with certainty whether the softness of Hg(II) ion is responsible for this. Hg-S bond is not improbable. But Hg(II) tends to form linear bonds and these are

obviously N-Hg-N bonds. Irving and William's order is not followed by the divalent metal ions of the first transitional series. The order is Cu > Co > Mn > Zn > Ni.

The high position of Co(II) and Mn(II) in the stability sequence is remarkable. The order Co > Ni is also found by Vartak et al.⁹, Johnston et al.¹⁰, Kakkar et al.¹¹ and Agrawal et al.¹². Some attribute this to Jahn-Teller stabilisation of Co(II) similar to Cu(II) and to favourable entropy effect. High position of Mn(II) in the stability sequence is also observed by earlier workers¹³⁻¹⁹. The pH range used was 5.6 to 7.9. In this range under nitrogen atmosphere Mn(II) is not oxidised to Mn(III). Kroll¹³ and Childs¹⁴ worked in still higher pH range. Since Mn(II) has no ligand field stabilisation energy and also very little tendency to back donate this high stability of Mn(II) cannot, however, be explained.

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